

MORPHOLOGY, THERMAL DEGRADATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIODEGRADABLE POLYESTER BLENDS AND NANOCOMPOSITES

Julia P. Mofokeng and Adriaan S. Luyt

Department of Chemistry, University of the Free State, Private Bag X13, Phuthaditjhaba,
9880, South Africa

Emails: MofokengJP@qwa.ufs.ac.za, LuytAS@qwa.ufs.ac.za

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ABSTRACT

Blends and nanocomposites of polylactic acid (PLA), poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-valerate) (PHBV), and polycaprolactone (PCL) were prepared through melt mixing and compression moulding. The morphologies of these samples were extensively studied, and selective localization of the titania nanoparticles was observed. Existing models (e.g. wetting coefficient model) based on surface free energy values were used to explain this observation. The selective localization of the nanoparticles had a very definite effect on the thermal degradation behaviour and mechanical properties of these nanocomposites. However, it was also found that each polymer in a blend had an influence on the degradation behaviour of the other polymer, even in the absence of nanoparticles.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past decades inorganic nanofillers have been used mainly in petroleum-based synthetic immiscible polymer blends. Their environmental unfriendliness motivated the use of biodegradable polymers, especially for packaging and short shelf-life product applications. Nanometre sized inorganic compounds such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂), zinc oxide (ZnO), silica (SiO₂), aluminium dioxide (Al₂O₃), and silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) were tried as fillers in fabrics and polymers to improve the tribological properties. TiO₂ has received most of the attention because of its good thermal stability, accessibility, and catalytic properties. It is generally used for various applications such as photo-electrochemical activity, solar energy conversion, photocatalysis, UV detection, ultrasonic sensing, and as a promising material in applications such as water or wastewater treatment. Its environmental compatibility, non-toxicity, and low price are some of its practical advantages [1-8].

Biodegradable polymers, and polymers derived from renewable resources, currently attract a lot of attention due to their environmental friendliness, since they combine biodegradability, compostability, and compatibility. They can be recycled or disposed of without harming the environment, and by using different waste forms they can be biodegraded to be used as fertilizers for crops [9]. One such a polymer, poly(lactic acid) (PLA), has been extensively investigated over the past decades, and it is a biodegradable, bio-absorbable, and renewable thermoplastic polyester derived mainly from corn starch. It is a useful material in substituting the petroleum-based polymers used in packaging, due to its good mechanical strength, processability, and energy saving recycling in which it is degraded by addition into a suitable compost where degradation will take place at ambient temperatures. Although PLA is so attractive, it has some limitations that limit its wide-spread use. These include poor toughness, slow degradation, hydrophobicity, lack of reactive side-chain groups, and low thermal stability [10-13]. Thermal stability is an important property, because it impacts on the time and temperature associated with the processing, service lifetime, and storage of the materials. Several factors like absorbed moisture, molecular weight, residual monomers, and metal catalysts affect the thermal stability of PLA, which can be improved by blending with other thermally stable polymers or by filling it with thermally stable inorganic nanofillers [14].

Blends of PLA and PCL have been reported to be immiscible, with poor mechanical properties because of their incompatibility [13,15,16]. Inorganic nanoparticles have lately been used to compatibilize this kind of blend, and to balance and tailor it to the desired properties needed for specific applications, mostly the thermal stability [17,18]. The thermal stability and morphology of individual PLA and PCL filled with inorganic/organic micro- and nanofillers have been studied [4,19-22], and it was reported that the fillers deteriorate the thermal stability of the polymers by catalysing the thermal degradation. The morphologies of the materials are controlled by whether the filler is functionalised or not. Severe aggregation of the nanofiller has been reported to decrease the thermal stability of the polymers, mostly for non-functionalised nanofillers.

PLA/PCL blends were widely studied over the past decade [11,13,23-29], and most of these studies reported a phase separated structure with discrete PLA domains in a continuous PCL phase, and in which the morphologies were stabilised by nanofillers. The nanofiller either selectively localised in one of the two phases in the blend, on the interface, or in both the interface and one of the phases. This selective localisation of the filler is determined by the large difference in the affinity, which is closely related to the surface properties of the different components, between the nanofiller and the two matrix components in the blend [30,31]. A number of studies reported on the dynamic mechanical properties of these materials. Cabedo *et al.* [11] and Jain *et al.* [13] studied the dynamic mechanical properties of PLA/PCL blends in the presence of respectively clay and micro-talc. They reported a decrease in the storage modulus (E') of PLA as a result of a plasticization effect of PCL on PLA. The storage modulus, however, increased in the presence of fillers, but was still lower than that of neat PLA. This was attributed to the inherent stiffness of talc and clay, which introduced a rigid interface in the blend. Wu *et al.* [27,28] reported an improvement in the miscibility between PLA and PCL when multiwalled carbon nanotubes were added, which was attributed to the emulsification that occurred at the interface in the presence of the amphiphilic carboxylic MWCNTs, leading to a thermodynamic stabilization of the interface.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Transmission electron microscopy images of (a) 70/30 w/w PLA/PCL and (b) 30/70 w/w PLA/PCL, both mixed with 5 wt.% TiO_2 nanoparticles (sizes < 25 nm before mixing). From these images it is clear that (i) the nanoparticles were fairly well dispersed in PLA and on the PLA-PCL interface, with some very large agglomerates, (ii) there were almost no nanoparticles in the PCL phase, (iii) the PCL forms ellipsoids of about $1.5 \times 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in the PLA matrix, and (iv) the PLA forms much larger ellipsoids with some indication of a co-continuous morphology.

	Contact angle / deg		Surface energy / mN m ⁻¹		
	H ₂ O	CH ₂ I ₂	γ	γ^d	γ^p
PLA	44.7 ± 1.0	35.4 ± 0.0	62.0	41.8	20.2
PCL	60.2 ± 0.8	27.0 ± 0.5	55.8	45.4	10.4
TiO₂	19.7	10.1	80.7	46.4	34.3

Table 1: Contact angles of PLA, PCL and TiO₂. The TiO₂ contact angle was taken from the literature [30] (γ = surface free energy, γ^d = dispersive component of surface free energy, γ^p = polar component of surface free energy)

Component pair	Interfacial tension / mN m ⁻¹
PLA/PCL	1.7
PLA/TiO ₂	2.0
PCL/TiO ₂	6.9

Table 2: Interfacial tension values calculated using the geometric-mean equation

($\gamma_{12} = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - 2\sqrt{\gamma_1^d \cdot \gamma_2^d + \gamma_1^p \cdot \gamma_2^p}$ where γ_{12} = interfacial tension between components 1 and 2 in the blend, γ_1 and γ_2 are the total surface energies of components 1 and 2, γ_1^d and γ_2^d are the dispersive surface energies of components 1 and 2, and γ_1^p and γ_2^p are the polar surface energies of the components in the nanocomposites)

The surface properties in Tables 1 and 2 indicate that the interfacial tension between PCL and the TiO₂ nanoparticles is quite high (6.9 mN m⁻¹), probably because of the difference between the polar components of their surface free energies. When there is a large difference between the polar components of the surface free energy, the two phases will probably not be compatible and therefore the nanoparticles will preferably disperse in the phase which has a more comparable polar component, in this case PLA.

Figure 2: Effect of blending and filler addition on the temperature at 50% mass loss of PLA (left) and PCL (right) in the PLA/PCL blends and nanocomposites. The thermal stability of both PLA and PCL decreases (from 357 to 350 °C for PLA, and from 424 to 409 °C for PCL) with an increase in the amount of the other polymer in the blend. The reason for the decrease in the thermal stability of PCL is due to the presence of the less thermally stable PLA. One would expect the thermal stability of PLA to increase in the presence of PCL, because PCL is more thermally stable than PLA. The decrease in PLA's thermal stability is probably the result of the incompatibility of the two polymers.

Figure 3: Activation energy vs. extent of degradation for PCL, PLA, 97/3 w/w PCL/TiO₂ and 97/3 w/w PLA/TiO₂. E_a of neat PCL increased almost linearly with extent of mass loss from 131 to 183 kJ mol⁻¹. The activation energies of PCL are significantly higher in the presence of the nanoparticles, which could signify an improvement in the thermal stability of PCL. However, it is quite possible that it is not the thermal stability which was improved, but the nanoparticles interacting with the degradation volatiles, delaying their diffusion out of the molten polymer blend. The activation energies of PLA are much higher than those of PCL, starting at 185 kJ mol⁻¹ and increasing almost linearly to 220 kJ mol⁻¹ with increasing extent of mass loss. This indicates that the degradation rates of PLA have a stronger dependence on temperature than those of PCL. The presence of TiO₂ in PLA reduced the activation energy of degradation of PLA. This indicates that the TiO₂ nanoparticles must have had a catalytic effect on the degradation of PLA. However, a conclusion like this cannot be made with absolute certainty, because ‘degradation’ in this case is monitored in terms of mass loss when the volatile degradation products evaporate from the degrading sample, and the diffusion of the volatile degradation products out of the sample and their evaporation may be retarded through interaction between these degradation products and the dispersed nanoparticles.

Figure 4: Activation energy vs. extent of degradation curves for 50/50 w/w PLA/PCL without and with 3 wt% TiO₂. The first half of each graph is related to the PLA degradation, and the second half to that of PCL. The activation energy of degradation of the blend increased from about 141 kJ mol⁻¹ to about 183 kJ mol⁻¹. The degradation activation energy for the PLA phase in the blend is therefore significantly lower than that of unblended PLA, which is in line with its reduced thermal stability in the presence of PCL, while the degradation activation energy of PCL is slightly higher than that of unblended PCL. In the presence of the nanoparticles the activation energy is higher for the PLA in the blend, but lower for the PCL in the blend. Several factors may contribute to changes in the degradation

kinetics of the different components in a blend and a nanocomposite. Firstly there is the catalysing effect of the nanoparticles, which may be more prevalent in the case of PLA. Secondly there is the interaction between the nanoparticles and the volatile degradation products, which may retard the diffusion of these products out of the sample. In this case different products may interact differently with the nanoparticles, and the adsorption of one or more of the volatile substances onto the nanoparticles may affect the extent of influence of the nanoparticles on the other products. The evaporation of PLA degradation products may also accelerate the release of PCL degradation products.

Figure 5: The E' curves of neat PLA, neat PCL, PLA/PCL blends and PLA/PCL/TiO₂ nanocomposites (a) 70/30, (b) 50/50, and 30/70 PLA/PCL with 1,3, and 5 wt% TiO₂

Figure 6: The E'' curves of neat PLA, neat PCL, PLA/PCL blends and PLA/PCL/TiO₂ nanocomposites (a) 70/30, (b) 50/50, and 30/70 PLA/PCL with 1,3, and 5 wt% TiO₂

Figure 7: The $\tan \delta$ curves of neat PLA, neat PCL, PLA/PCL blends and PLA/PCL/TiO₂ nanocomposites (a) 70/30, (b) 50/50, and 30/70 PLA/PCL with 1, 3, and 5 wt% TiO₂

The storage moduli around -80 °C (which is below the T_{gs} of PLA and PCL) of all the PLA/PCL blends and nanocomposites are closely the same or lower than the storage moduli of the neat polymers (Figure 5). The storage modulus at 20 °C, which is between the glass transition temperatures of the two polymers in the blend, shows a decrease with an increase in the content of the lower modulus PCL

in the blend. This is normal for immiscible and incompatible polymer blends, which is clearly the case for the PLA/PCL blend. The loss modulus results (Figure 6) show that the glass transition temperatures of PLA and PCL changed very little as a result of blending. This confirms the complete immiscibility of the two polymers. The presence and content of TiO₂ nanoparticles in the blends also had little influence on the glass transition temperatures. The tan δ curves (Figure 7) show three transitions: the first is the glass transition of PCL, the second the glass transition of PLA, and the third the cold crystallization of PLA. The intensities of the glass transition (which is the β -relaxation in the case of semi-crystalline polymers like PCL and PHBV) peaks are lower for PCL in the blends (Figure 8 and Table 2), which was expected because of the decreasing amounts of PCL in the blends. The presence and amount of titania filler had little effect on the maximum tan δ values for PCL, and no trend is observed. This is probably because PCL anyway shows extremely low damping as a result of its fairly high chain mobility, and because there were very few nanoparticles in contact with PCL. The intensity of the glass transition peaks for PLA increases with increasing PCL content, although this peak was not completely formed for 30/70 w/w PLA/PCL because of PCL melting which interrupted the DMA analysis. This increase is the result of larger PLA chain mobility in the presence of the softer PCL. Unfortunately the effect of the nanoparticles on the PLA chain mobility could not be determined from these results because of the interruption of the DMA analyses in this temperature region.

Figure 8: DSC cooling (left) and second heating (right) curves of PLA, PCL and their blends

From Figures 8 and 9 the following may be concluded:

- (1) The presence of PLA has an observable influence on PCL crystallization. PCL crystallizes at a higher temperature, and the crystallization occurred over a much narrower temperature range.
- (2) The glass transition of PLA overlaps with PCL melting so that it is not visible in the heating curves of the blends. It is, however, clearly visible in the cooling curves of the blends.
- (3) PCL melting is not influenced by the presence of PLA, while it seems as if the PLA cold crystallization and melting depends on the blend morphology.
- (4) The stepscan DSC results show two irreversible crystallization transitions for PLA at about 90 °C and 145 °C, instead of the single cold crystallization observed at about 120 °C observed in the normal DSC curve. The PLA also shows a double melting peak in the reversible curve, with an underlying irreversible melting at a slightly higher temperature, while the normal DSC curves show a single melting peak following cold crystallization. It does not seem as if the presence of titania had a significant influence on the PLA crystallization and melting behaviour.

- (5) PCL shows a well-defined melting peak around 60 °C which consists of reversible and irreversible components. In this case it also seems as if the presence of titania did not have a significant influence.

Figure 9: Stepscan (modulated) DSC curves showing the reversible and irreversible thermal events during the heating of (a) 75/25 w/w PLA/PCL, (b) 25/75 w/w PLA/PCL, (c) 75/25 w/w PLA/PCL + 3 phr TiO₂, and (d) 25/75 w/w PLA/PCL + 3 phr TiO₂

3 CONCLUSIONS

The nanoparticles were primarily dispersed in the PLA phase, and on the interface, of the PLA/PCL blends. This was attributed to affinity because of small differences between the relative polarities of the nanoparticles and PLA. Neat PLA had a lower thermal stability than PCL, but a higher activation energy of degradation. This was attributed to the more complex degradation mechanism(s) of PLA. Blending seemingly decreased the thermal stability of both polymers, but an explanation for this observation is not immediately obvious. It is possible that, since ‘degradation’ in this case was monitored through TGA analysis, the escape of the volatile degradation products of one polymer could have been influenced by the presence of the other polymer. The presence of the TiO₂ nanoparticles improved the thermal stabilities of both polymers in the blends, and influenced the volatilization of the degradation products. This influence was attributed to a combination of the catalytic effect of the nanoparticles and their interaction with the volatile degradation products. The dynamic mechanical properties of PLA/PCL were little influenced by blending and the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles. The presence of the other component, and the morphology of the blends, had an influence on the crystallization and melting behaviour of respectively PLA and PCL in PLA/PCL blends. The presence of nanoparticles, however, did not seem to have any influence.

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